

Assessment of Knowledge and Attitude of Veterinary Drug Vendors and Poultry Farmers on use of Antibiotics in Poultry in Sokoto Metropolis

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Questionnaires were administered to 50 veterinary drug retailers and 50 poultry farm workers to assess their knowledge and attitude on the commonly used antibiotics in poultry in Sokoto metropolis. The respondents were guided on how to answer the questionnaire. From the responses, 100% of drug sellers were males and those with 5-10 years experience in the practice had highest number. 100% had western education out of which 90% had tertiary education. Combined drugs were the most dispensed (44%) followed by Oxytetracycline single drug (22%). Among the drug retailers, 42% had professional knowledge on antibiotics, 68% dispense drugs on prescription by veterinarian and 22% had knowledge on antibiotic resistance. Out of the 50 poultry farm workers that responded to the questionnaire, 82% were males, 44% had tertiary education, and 32% had only Islamic education. Among the respondents, farm managers had the highest number (32%) Most known poultry disease among the respondents was Newcastle disease and knowledge on the diseases was 86%. Among the most frequently used drug combinations, Gendox had the highest frequency of usage (30%), followed by Tyloxox 28%, Keproceryl 20%, Neoceryl 16% and Amoxycol 6%. Among the farm workers, 22% had professional knowledge on antibiotics, 88% dispense drugs on prescription by veterinarian and 48% had knowledge on antibiotic resistance. Among the respondents, 92% administer complete prescribed medication while 50% observe drug withdrawal period. The study has unveiled the knowledge and attitude of veterinary drug sellers and poultry farmers on antibiotic in Sokoto metropolis. Updating the level of knowledge and skill of paravets through various fora, standardized curriculum, regular training programs, and enhanced skills in diagnosis could help overcome the challenges of irrational use of antibiotics.

Key words: Antibiotics, Drug retailers, farmers, knowledge assessment Sokoto.,

INTRODUCTION

The poultry industry is characterized mainly by backyard, small scale or medium scale commercial production system. The major economic activity of the people of Sokoto State is agriculture and poultry production has taken a high percentage of the sector. Poultry diseases are at the increase globally causing a considerable threat

to global public health and reducing poultry production output. Antibiotics are therapeutics used in treatment of many infectious diseases caused by bacterial agents and some other pathogens. Drugs used in the treatment of animal diseases are being sold and used indiscriminately by non-professionals whom have little or no knowledge on the drugs there by increasing the risk of treatment failure and antimicrobial resistance (Gržinić *et al.*, 2023).

Antimicrobial agents have been widely used since the 1950s in poultry for improvement of feed efficiency and

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as growth promoters (Niewold, 2007; Torok *et al.*, 2011). They are also used to treat poultry diseases (Torok *et al.*, 2011). Worldwide, 73% of all antimicrobial agents available in most retail stores are utilized in food animals (Van Boeckel *et al.*, 2015). These antimicrobial agents are usually administered through various routes, ranging from injection to orally in feed and drinking water, with permission of use varying between countries and regions (Rosengren *et al.*, 2008). The use of antimicrobial agents for growth promotion in food animals is all over world, but it was banned by the European Union (EU) in 2006 and in the U.S. in 2017 (Rahman *et al.*, 2022).

Antibiotics have been used widely in poultry industry in order to treat and prevent infectious bacterial diseases. They have also been used at low levels in feed as growth promoters. Such practice has improved poultry performance effectively and economically but an increase in numbers of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains like *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus* sp. and *Enterococcus* sp. did occur which can be transmitted from poultry to humans through the food chain with serious consequences on public health (Mehdi *et al.*, 2018). Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is widely considered a global public health threat, with the use of antimicrobials in poultry production considered one of the contributing factors. This is potentiated due to limited knowledge of danger associated with antimicrobial resistance by both veterinary drugs vendors and poultry farmers. This unchecked dependence on antimicrobials results in their unregulated use and abuse in human and animal health, resulting in AMR. The problem therefore needs to be addressed (Muaz *et al.*, 2018). Excessive reliance on antimicrobial agents results in their misuse and/or abuse in human therapies, animal husbandry and aquaculture (Muteeb *et al.* 2023; Holmes *et al.*, 2016).

In quantitative terms, the amount of antimicrobial drugs used in livestock globally was estimated to be 63,151 tonnes in 2010, due to the rising demand for livestock products by the human population in middle-income countries, it is expected to increase to 67% by 2030, reaching approximately 105,500 tonnes. (de Mesquita *et al.*, 2022).

One of the challenges faced by paravets which eventually had direct effect on poultry production is inefficient delivery of animal husbandry services to farmers. These challenges include lack of proper record, lack of standardized curriculum and limited skills in diagnosis, lack of regular training programmes to update knowledge and skill and ethical issues with role obligations (Kumar and Meena, 2021). Food safety of animal products due to overuse of antibiotic drugs is a challenge which paravets and farmers could not recognize its importance. Paravets, drug sellers and farmers lack sufficient knowledge and awareness about the drug withdrawal period, as a result of which overuse

of antibiotics aggravates the pace of the spread of antibiotic resistance leading to inefficiency of drugs to cure diseases (Landers *et al.*, 2012).

This study aimed at assessment of compliance to vaccination and its impact on backyard production in Sokoto metropolis.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

The study was carried out in Sokoto metropolis Sokoto State. The State is located in the extreme northwest of Nigeria sharing border with the Republic of Niger and Benin to the North and West respectively. It also shares border with Kebbi State to the south and Zamfara state to the East. Its capital, the city of Sokoto is located near the confluence of the Sokoto River and the Rima River with the GPS coordinates 13° 5' 0" N and 5° 15' 0" E. The climate has distinct wet and dry seasons. Sokoto is one of the warmest regions in Nigeria with an average daily high temperature of 37°C. During the cool harmattan season from October to February, the temperature is low, about 15.5°C (Wikipedia, 2024)).

Study Design

Questionnaires were designed targeted at 100 respondents, 50 working in randomly selected poultry farms and 50 working in Veterinary drug shop owners in Sokoto metropolis. The modified questionnaires were designed to assess knowledge of poultry farmers and drug vendors on poultry drugs in Sokoto metropolis. The questionnaire was administered by visitation to poultry farms and veterinary drug retailers within the metropolis. The targeted respondents were guided appropriately. The questionnaire was designed to assess knowledge of the respondents on poultry diseases, vaccination and its importance in poultry health. Generated data was analyzed and conclusions and recommendations were made.

Data Collection

The data was collected through the use of questionnaires designed based on the assessment of knowledge of poultry drugs by poultry farmers and drug vendors in Sokoto metropolis. The questionnaire was administered by visitation to randomly selected poultry farms and veterinary drug retailers within Sokoto metropolis. Awareness was created to the respondents on the purpose, and their willingness and consent were sought. Direct one on one interview with farm workers and the drug vendors was conducted. The farm workers included

Table 1. The survey instrument and the scoring system used to assess the knowledge and perceptions of veterinary drug retailers

Instrument	Response
Knowledge (<i>n</i> = 50)	
Duration in the job	Years
Level of education	Islamic education only, primary education, secondary education, tertiary education
Most sold single and combined antibiotics	Oxytetracycline, Tylosin, Gentamicin, Sulfa, Enrofloxacin, Gendox, Tylocox, Keproceryl, Neoceryl, Amoxycol
Can poultry be resistant to drugs?	No, Yes, I don't know
Do you give drug based on veterinarian's prescription?	No, Yes
Do you recommend observing withdrawal period?	No, Yes
Do you believe there is excessive use of antibiotic in poultry?	No, Yes, I dont know
Do you advise to stop treatment when improvement is observed in birds?	No, Yes
Which of these diseases are you aware of?	Newcastle, Gumboro, Avian influenza, Fowl typhoid, Coccidiosis, Infectious coryza, Fowl pox
Antibiotics should only be prescribed when needed	No, Yes
Only vets should be allowed to prescribe antibiotics	No, Yes

Table 2. The survey instrument and the scoring system used to assess the knowledge and perceptions of poultry farm workers

Instrument	Response
Knowledge (<i>n</i> = 50)	
Staff category	Farm owner, Manager, Laborer, Security personnel
Level of education	Islamic education only, primary education, secondary education, tertiary education
Most used single and combined antibiotics	Oxytetracycline, Tylosin, Gentamicin, Sulfa, Enrofloxacin, Gendox, Tylocox, Keproceryl, Neoceryl, Amoxycol
Can poultry be resistant to drugs?	No, Yes, I don't know
Do you give drug based on veterinarian's prescription?	No, Yes
Do you observe withdrawal period?	No, Yes
Do you believe there is excessive use of antibiotic in poultry?	No, Yes, I don't know
Do you stop treatment when you observe improvements in your birds?	No, Yes
Which of these diseases are you aware of?	Newcastle, Gumboro, Avian influenza, Fowl typhoid, Coccidiosis, Infectious coryza, Fowl pox
Antibiotics should only be prescribed when needed	No, Yes
Only vets should be allowed to prescribe antibiotics	No, Yes
Can antibiotics be used to treat viral, fungal, or parasitic infections in birds?	No, Yes, I don't know
Can ABR organisms be transferred to humans from poultry products?	No, Yes, I don't know

Table 3: Population distribution of Veterinary drug retailers by sex, literacy level and knowledge of drugs

Factors	Frequency N=50	Percentage
Sex		
Male	50	100
Female	0	0
Duration in the job		
0-5 years	23	46
5-10 years	20	40
10-20 years	4	8
More than 20 years	3	6
Literacy level		
Islamic education only	0	0
Secondary education and below	5	10
Tertiary education	45	90
Most dispensed drug		
Oxytetracycline	11	22
Enrofloxacin	3	6
Sulfa drugs	4	8
Gentamicin	1	2
Tylosine	9	18
Combination of antibiotics	22	44
Most dispensed antibiotic combination		
Tylodox	15	30
Gendox	13	26
Neoceryl	6	12
Keproceryl	16	32
Amoxycol	0	0
Professional knowledge on antibiotics	21	42
Dispensed on prescription by Veterinarian	34	68
Knowledge on antibiotic resistance	11	22

Table 4: Population distribution of poultry farmers by sex, literacy level, and experience in farm.

Factors	Frequency N=50	Percentage
Sex		
Male	41	82
Female	9	0
Literacy level		
Tertiary education	22	44
Secondary education	4	8
Primary education	8	16
Islamic education only	16	32
Staff category		
Farm owner	4	8
Manager	18	32
Laborer	22	44
Security personnel	6	12
Knowledge of farmers on common poultry diseases		
Newcastle disease	43	86
Avian Influenza	30	60
Gumboro	12	24
Fowl pox	40	80
Fowl typhoid	37	74
Coccidiosis	33	66

Table 4. Contd.

Infectious coryza	12	24
<i>Most used antibiotic combination</i>		
Tylodox	14	28
Gendox	15	30
Neoceryl	8	16
Keproceryl	10	20
Amoxycol	3	6
Professional Knowledge on antibiotics	11	22
Follow prescription by Veterinarian	42	88
Knowledge of antibiotic resistance	24	48
Completion of therapy	46	92
Observing drug withdrawal period	25	50

the owners, farm managers, farm laborers and farm security personel. While some filled the questionnaire after being guided appropriately, others whom had no western knowledge were assisted by entering the answers they provided. The study period was from April to July 2024. Data was collected from Sokoto north, Sokoto south and Wamakko Local Government areas of the state.

Data Analysis

Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS[®]) 21.0 version was used for statistical analysis. The data generated from poultry farms and veterinary drug retailers were carefully analyzed using descriptive statistics to calculate frequencies and percentages, and the results were clearly indicated.

RESULTS

From the generated data, among the 50 veterinary drug retailers, 100% were males. For duration in practice of selling animal drugs, 46% had 0-5 years experience, 40% had 5-10 years experience, 8% had 10-20 years' experience while 6 % had over 20 years in the practice. Among the respondents, 100% had western education out of which 90% had tertiary education while 10% had below tertiary education. Combined drugs were the most dispensed (44%) followed by Oxytetracycline 22%, Tylosin 18%, Sulfa 8%, Enrofloxacin 6% and Gentamicin 2%. Among the most frequently used drug combinations, Keproceryl had the highest frequency of 32%, followed by Tylodox 30%, Gendox 26%, Neoceryl 12%. Among the drug retailers, 42% had professional knowledge on antibiotics, 68% dispense drugs on prescription by veterinarian and 22% had knowledge on antibiotic resistance (shown in Table 3). Out of the 50 poultry farm workers interviewed within Sokoto metropolis, 82% of the

respondents were males, 44% had tertiary education, 24% had below tertiary education and 32% had only Islamic education. Among the respondents, farm owner were 8%, farm managers 32%, laborers 44% and security personnel 12%. Most known poultry disease among the respondents was Newcastle disease and percentage knowledge on the diseases was 86%, Avian pox 80%, Typhoid 74%, Coccidiosis 66%, Avian influenza 60%, Gumboro and Coryza 24% each. Among the most frequently used drug combinations, Gendox had the highest frequency of usage (30%), followed by Tylodox 28%, Keproceryl 20%, Neoceryl 16% and Amoxycol 6%. Among the farm workers, 22% had professional knowledge on antibiotics, 88% dispense drugs on prescription by veterinarian and 48% had knowledge on antibiotic resistance. Among the respondents, 92% complete prescribed medication while 50% observe drug withdrawal period (shown in Table 4).

DISCUSSION

In this research work, the result showed compliance of majority of the targeted respondents to participate in answering the questionnaire. Out of the respondents, 100% are males, involved in drug retail business and 82% among farm workers are males while only 18% of farm workers are females. This could be related to cultural and religious norms in the study area where it is believed females have specific work nature acceptable by the society.

The study also showed that 46% of drug retailers which were the majority, engaged in the job between 0-5 years back, indicating increase in interest in the business. This is either due to increase in number of professionals in that aspect or difficulty in securing government job rendering youth to alternatively embark on other jobs as supported by Ajani and Oyekola (2019).

In the recent years, there has been increase in

formulation of combined powdered veterinary drugs aimed at achieving better result compared to use of single antibiotic. From this study, the result showed Keproceryl, Gendox and Tyloxox to have higher usage compared to other drug combinations. Keproceryl constitutes antibiotics and vitamins which decreases farmers need to buy more than one drug at a time, Gendox and Tyloxox have been found to yield good result in the treatment of digestive and respiratory diseases, as such, their demand is in the increase. Among Single antibiotics, Oxytetracycline had highest frequency of usage (22%) this could be attributed to popularity of the drug and its therapeutic effect on wide range of microbials even though there have been several reports on resistance of bacteria to Oxytetracycline. Oxytet resistance Mungadi and Abdullahi (2024) reported high resistance of E coli isolated from chickens in Sokoto (70%) to Oxytetracycline

Newcastle was found to be most popular disease among farmers with 86% knowledge on the disease. This is possibly due to it being endemic in the study area, affecting all types and age groups of birds and causing devastating loss to farmers. Avian pox follows 80%, followed by Fowl typhoid 74%, Coccidiosis 66%, Avian influenza 60%, Gumboro and Coryza 24%. All these diseases are among the causes of losses by farmers. Gumboro lacks much popularity as the signs are always confused with diseases having similar clinical signs in chickens like Salmonellosis. Mera and Adenrele (2020), reported Newcastle to be the most common known disease by farmers in Sokoto metropolis, also Ibitoye *et al.* (2013) reported ND as the highest occurring disease in the Area. But on the contrary, Adamu *et al.* (2009) reported Gumboro as the most common disease in the area.

Among the farm workers, 22% had professional knowledge on antibiotics, 88% dispense drugs on prescription by veterinarian and 48% had knowledge on antibiotic resistance. There has been a great concern on the way and manner para vets take the place of trained veterinary doctors, prescribing drugs to farmers whom have limited knowledge on the profession and practice.

Report by Ajieh and Oyibojoba (2018), in research to determine constraints and adoption of practices in poultry production in Delta State, Nigeria mentioned that the major constraints to poultry production include the high cost of veterinary services, among other factors. This is a similar situation in Sokoto State, Nigeria, where many poultry farmers go for cheaper services from non-professionals, which leads to unprofessional use of antibiotics in poultry, resulting to antimicrobial resistance. Among the respondents, 92% complete doses of prescribed medication while 50% observe drug withdrawal period. These two aforementioned are among factors leading to antimicrobial resistance.

CONCLUSION

The study has unveiled the knowledge and attitude of veterinary drug sellers and poultry farmers on antibiotic in Sokoto metropolis. It has been found that majority of the drug sellers prescribe medications to farmers who are looking for cheaper services. There is the need therefore for creating awareness by the agencies concerned such as the Veterinarians, Local authorities and civil society organizations involved to help in reducing irrational use of drugs in poultry. Updating the level of knowledge and skill of paravets through various fora, standardized curriculum regular training programs, and enhanced skills in diagnosis could help overcome the challenges of irrational use of antibiotics.

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